

Advanced Filament Wound Composites

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ABSTRACT

Filament winding has been an active growing reinforced plastics process for more than thirty years. Filament wound composites have ranged from rocket motor cases and launch tubes in the earlier days to automotive leaf springs today. The intent of this paper is to acquaint the reader with modern day filament winding, including basic products, process and machinery. A general review of filament winding as a process will update the reinforced plastics industry with modern day advancements. A basic review of products will show the broad spectrum the filament winding industry is now covering. Automation of the entire filament winding process will also be discussed. Future applications and filament winding techniques will also be presented.

